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The Needs of Foreign Language Teachers in Czech Schools: A Qualitative Insight into Classroom Practice

Introduction

The aim of this qualitative research was to gain an in-depth understanding of the needs of foreign language teachers—specifically those teaching English, German, French, and Spanish—in planning and delivering lessons, as well as in substituting for absent colleagues. Our goal was to obtain a comprehensive view of teachers' everyday practice and to identify key areas where they feel a lack of support (e.g., methodological guidance, material preparation, technical equipment, etc.). The research questions were designed to uncover specific challenges and needs both inside and outside the school environment. Through interviews, we sought to capture an informed picture of teachers' daily concerns and areas requiring further attention.

Research Sample

The study involved 50 foreign language teachers from over 40 primary and secondary schools across the Czech Republic. Respondents came from diverse regions, including major cities (Prague, Brno, Ostrava), smaller towns, and rural schools in various districts. The sample encompassed a range of school types: urban and rural schools, grammar schools, language institutions, and private educational organizations. This diversity was intended to ensure a wide spectrum of teaching conditions and professional experiences. Participants' teaching experience ranged from a few years to more than two decades. Regarding the languages taught, the majority (approximately 60%) were English teachers, while the remainder comprised teachers of German, French, and Spanish, more or less evenly distributed. Some respondents taught multiple languages concurrently. This variety—in terms of

environment, school size, socioeconomic conditions, and long-term experience—enabled us to gather a broad range of perspectives on foreign language teaching.

Research Implementation

The research was conducted in October–November 2024 by a five-member team from *Foxino*, a company developing educational technologies for language learning. The team included specialists in product research and UX/UI design, as well as pedagogical experts in educational content development. The study preparation included designing a semi-structured interview guide with open-ended questions, covering key topics related to teaching practice (see below). Interviews were conducted by individual team members, all of whom had research and teaching experience, while adhering to standard ethical procedures (e.g., informed consent). Each interview lasted approximately 60 minutes and was conducted flexibly—some in person at schools, others via video calls, and several by phone depending on technical constraints and respondent preferences. The only output from the interviews was structured written notes; no audio or video recordings were made. Thanks to meticulous note-taking, the team acquired a rich dataset for subsequent analysis.

Thematic Areas

The interviews focused from the outset on several core aspects of everyday foreign language teaching. Key thematic areas included:

- **Lesson Planning:** We explored how teachers search for and compile materials for their lessons. We were interested in how much time they spend preparing each class, their sources of teaching materials (original ideas, books, online resources), and whether they have access to teaching guides or shared lesson plans. We also discussed collaboration barriers and the time pressure associated with preparation.
- **Digital Tools:** Teachers shared their experiences using technology in language instruction. We asked about apps, online platforms, and interactive tools (e.g., tablets, smartboards)—what they use, what helps, and what they lack. We also inquired about perceived barriers (e.g., weak internet, lack of devices) and how they envision better support for IT tools.
- **Administrative Tasks:** We examined the administrative workload teachers face, such as grading, test creation, planning, reporting, form-filling, and communication with parents or school management. We asked how much time they devote to these tasks and how they perceive their impact on teaching time.
- **Teachers' Language Confidence:** An important topic was how confident teachers feel in their command of the target language. We asked whether they

ever feel insecure explaining grammar or pronunciation, how they handle complex classroom discussions, and whether they would welcome further language or methodological development.

- **Support in Substitution:** We explored how teachers cope when substituting for colleagues on short notice. We asked whether they are given necessary information and materials (lesson plans, topics, aids), and how they manage improvisation. We discussed their vision for better support (e.g., ready-made backup plans, substitution tips).
- **Need for Methodological and Professional Development:** In a broader context, we asked what ideal support for teachers should look like. We explored whether they miss sharing good practices, mentoring from experienced colleagues, specialized training, or community platforms for exchanging ideas. The goal was to identify aspects that go beyond daily routines but would support long-term professional growth.

Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using a traditional qualitative approach, with the full research team involved in interpretation. First, we conducted open coding of the interview notes. Each transcript was carefully reviewed and segmented into meaning units assigned short descriptive codes (e.g., "long prep time," "weak Wi-Fi," "substitution stress"). This phase was carried out independently by two researchers to capture as wide a range of themes as possible. The team then consolidated the coding schemes to ensure consistency. A thematic analysis followed: similar codes were grouped into broader categories aligned with the main interview topics (see above). For example, codes related to paperwork, documentation, and test preparation were merged under "administrative burden," while notes on apps and school technology fell under "digital tools and support." The process was iterative; as new insights emerged, new codes or refined categories were added. Regular team discussions helped calibrate interpretations—researchers cross-validated meanings and resolved differing viewpoints to ensure the final themes faithfully reflected teachers' perspectives. We also partially quantified the data by counting how many teachers mentioned each topic, allowing us to state, for instance, that a majority or minority experienced a certain issue. This combination of open coding and thematic grouping yielded a deep insight into teachers' experiences and strengthened the conclusions.

Key Findings

The interview analysis revealed recurring problems and needs reported by foreign language teachers. The main findings included:

- **Administrative Burden and Lesson Planning:** Teachers reported that administrative duties (creating and grading tests, reporting grades, filling out forms, scheduling tests, etc.) consume a significant portion of their weekly workload.

“Every week I spend about eight hours on admin tasks because I still grade tests by hand and prepare student lists,” noted one English teacher.

This time estimate (approx. 8 hours weekly) was confirmed by the majority as realistic. Teachers feel that administrative load diverts time from actual teaching and unnecessarily extends lesson preparation.

“I feel like I start planning from scratch every year because we lack shared teaching materials. Prep takes much longer than it should,” added another teacher.

These statements underscore how the lack of shared resources and heavy admin workloads hinder pedagogical focus and innovation.

- **Student Attention and Lesson Pace:** A major theme was difficulty maintaining student attention and motivation. About 60% reported persistent issues with focus during class.

“My students struggle to stay focused,” shared one English teacher. Additionally, 73% felt that students often get bored due to inappropriate lesson pacing. Overall, 80% rated the pace of instruction as unsatisfactory—some students find it too slow and repetitive, others too fast. *“I think the pace is often too slow—we go over the same material again and again. That’s why many kids get bored,”* said a Spanish teacher.

These responses show that current pacing does not meet students' needs and contributes to classroom disengagement.

- **Language Confidence:** Roughly 30% of respondents admitted feeling uncertain in their own language use, especially when explaining complex grammar or pronunciation as non-native speakers.

“As a French teacher, I sometimes feel unsure when explaining difficult grammar. No one steps in to help—I have to figure it out on my own,” said one respondent. This highlights a desire for more language and methodological support. Many respondents expressed interest in further training or shared best practices.

- **Substitution and Improvisation:** Teachers often face sudden substitution assignments without adequate preparation.

“When I’m asked to cover for a colleague, I usually have to improvise—I don’t get any lesson plan or worksheets. It’s stressful,” one teacher explained. Many would welcome clearer protocols and pre-prepared backup plans. Lack of substitution support remains a significant source of stress and fatigue.

- **Digital Tools and Technical Support:** Many teachers raised concerns about inadequate equipment.

“We don’t have a modern smartboard or stable internet, so I rely on paper materials. With better tools, lessons would be more engaging,” said one respondent. Teachers expressed interest in using educational apps and online exercises but are limited by outdated technology or weak infrastructure.

- **Need for Methodological Support:** Finally, many teachers called for more systematic professional guidance.

“I’d like more methodological support and experience-sharing with colleagues. We often feel isolated—having a guide or community would simplify things,” said one teacher.

There is a clear interest in mentoring, workshops, and online forums focused on language teaching. The lack of structured methodological support represents a major gap in teachers’ professional development.

Synthesis of Key Trends

Based on these findings, key patterns emerged:

- Teachers face a heavy administrative load (approx. 8 hours weekly)
- 60% report poor student focus
- 80% are dissatisfied with the pace of instruction (with 73% noting student boredom)
- About one-third feel uncertain in their language skills
- Many call for improved infrastructure and stronger methodological peer support

The direct quotes above illustrate the diverse aspects of these challenges and offer a strong foundation for recommendations on how to develop supportive tools and practices in the education sector.

Sample Questionnaire**Respondent:** anonymized**School:** Rakovského Primary School, Central Bohemian Region**Subject:** English Language**Teaching Experience:** 11 years**School Type:** Lower Secondary School (Grades 6–9)**Mode of Instruction:** In-person

1. How much time per week do you spend on non-teaching administrative tasks (e.g. reports, grading, overviews for management)?

- Up to 2 hours
- 3–5 hours
- 6–10 hours
- More than 10 hours

Comment:

"I feel like a clerk – spreadsheets, reports, records. I often don't get around to lesson prep until after 9 p.m."

2. Which of the following statements best describes your lesson preparation?

- I always prepare lessons well in advance.
- I usually prepare the day before, sometimes in a rush.
- I only use the textbook and don't prepare anything additional.
- I prepare multiple versions of the lesson based on students' levels.

Comment:

"Sometimes I'd like to prepare differentiated lessons, but realistically, I'm just glad if I manage to prepare one version for everyone."

3. Do you have the opportunity to collaborate with colleagues on lesson planning?

- Yes, regularly
- Occasionally, when time allows
- No, everyone prepares on their own

Comment:

"Sometimes my colleague and I exchange worksheets, but formally, no systematic cooperation exists."

4. Does the unified pace of instruction suit all your students?

- Yes
- No

Comment:

"I have students in the same class who speak fluently and others who can't form basic sentences. I adapt the pace to the weaker ones, but the others get bored."

5. How many language proficiency levels do you currently deal with in a single class?

- One uniform level
 - 2 levels
 - 3 or more
-

6. How often do you struggle with student inattention or lack of interest during class?

- Rarely
- Occasionally
- Often
- Almost always

Comment:

"Without interactive elements and games, attention quickly drops. As soon as it's 'just exercises,' they're on their phones or doodling."

7. Do you feel confident in your language skills while teaching (e.g. answering student questions, pronunciation, advanced grammar)?

- Yes, always
- Mostly yes, but I sometimes hesitate
- No, I often feel unsure

Comment:

"I handle everyday situations fine, but when someone uses an idiom or asks about subtle nuances, I get unsure."

8. Do you use digital tools for lesson planning or teaching?

- Yes, regularly
- Occasionally
- No

Most commonly used tools:

Quizlet, custom PowerPoint presentations, Wordwall

9. What should an ideal lesson preparation tool include? (check all that apply)

- Automatic lesson generator by topic and level
 - Ability to modify prepared lessons
 - Sharing lesson plans with colleagues
 - Language support (notes, pronunciation, synonyms)
 - Integration with class records
 - Other:
-

10. How often do you cover someone else's lesson without prior preparation?

- Rarely
- 1–2 times a month
- Weekly
- More than once a week

Comment:

"I come into class and have no idea what to teach. I have to improvise or use an old worksheet."

11. Would being able to share a prepared lesson with another teacher (e.g. for substitution) be helpful to you?

- It would be very helpful
 - Maybe
 - I don't need it
-

12. How many minutes per week do you spend searching for suitable teaching materials?

- Up to 30 minutes
 - 30–60 minutes
 - More than 60 minutes
-

13. How often do you feel overwhelmed or uninspired when planning lessons?

- Rarely
- Occasionally

- Often
- Almost always

Comment:

"By the end of the semester, I go on autopilot—I just don't have the capacity to look for new ideas."

14. What would be the biggest benefit of a digital lesson planning tool for you?**Answer:**

"Time-saving, ready-made activity suggestions, ability to adapt by level, and quick sharing with colleagues."

15. Message for the developers:**Answer:**

"I don't need fancy features—just a tool that works fast, without training, and saves me time. Simplicity is key."